

STUDYING THE RESISTANCE OF PHOTORESISTORS THROUGH LIGHT INTENSITY

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Abstract: research paper provides an overview of the light sensitivity of photoresistors used in photosensors that detect the position of the sun in solar collectors, photovoltaic modules, and other devices.

Keywords: resistance, intensity, light, sun, photoresistor, photosensor, photovoltaic power stations,

Enter. The demand of the countries of the world for electricity is increasing day by day. Electricity plays an important role in the development of production, industry, science and technology. Many countries are worried about the increasing consumption of electricity, because natural energy reserves are exhausted and energy demand is increasing day by day. In particular, energy supply is a problem, so it is necessary to save it and choose an alternative way to obtain energy. Developing countries are gradually moving to the use of alternative energy sources, including Uzbekistan, which has already switched to the use of energy in this regard. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the use of solar energy is promising. It would not be wrong to say that solar panels are a huge source of

energy for us. The use of solar panels is definitely limited because a solar panel cannot collect a lot of energy while standing still. Nowadays, it is becoming more and more popular to use solar panels to make the most of every sunny day.

Photoresistor analysis. High-precision semiconductor devices are widely used to drive solar panels. One of these devices is a photoresistor, because it is very sensitive to external influences. A photoresistor is a semiconductor device whose resistance changes under the influence of light. All its properties definitely change with light intensity. Despite the fact that the resistance of photoresistors is several $100\text{M}\Omega$, under the influence of light, its resistance can decrease to $\text{m}\Omega$. It is convenient to control the solar panels through this property of the photoresistor.

The expression of photoresistor connection to light intensity is as follows.

$$R = \frac{R_0}{e^{\frac{ISt}{kT}}} \quad (1)$$

R_0 is the resistance of the photoresistor without light

R is the resistance when exposed to light.

From the first formula, it is known that the resistance of the photoresistor is inversely related to the light intensity. As the resistance value changes exponentially. For our experiment, we determine for the case that the light intensity is $1000\text{W}/\text{m}^2$ at $\text{AM}1.5\text{g}$. Using this formula, we made calculations through

the programming language. Through a programming language, we perform calculations. In this case, we performed calculations using the C# programming language. This programming language is very broad and easy to use. The C# programming language is the leading programming language in the world, and it is very efficient to create algorithms for relating physical entities and quantities. First we introduce our variables and constants. We will create an algorithm for it to perform calculations, and we will analyze it by saving the results obtained from the algorithm. In our experiment, the calculation algorithm determined the light intensity with an interval of 1Wt/m^2 , that is, it was calculated by increasing the light intensity by one standard. We created this graph from the results of the calculations.

Figure 1. Connection of photoresistor resistance to light intensity.

Summary. In conclusion, when we studied the sensitivity of photoresistor sensors to light, we found that they change their parameters better. Therefore, it is

reasonable to use photoresistor sensors for the solar tracking system of PV modules.

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